

Total Electron Content Variations at a Low Latitude East African Station and Its Comparison with IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 Models during Solar Cycle 24.

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Abstract: Ionospheric modelling is one of the most crucial approaches to study the activities of the ionosphere particularly in regions where experimental data are not readily available. This research aims to study the variations of Total Electron Content (TEC) in a low latitude east African station (Addis Ababa) by comparing experimental values of TEC from the Global Positioning System (GPS) with predicted data from IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models during solar cycle 24 using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) metric analysis approach. An hourly interval profile computed on seasonal basis were used to study the behaviors of TEC. A monthly interval error profile plotted on annual basis was also used to investigate the deviations of the models from the GPS values. This study analyzed TEC data from 2011 to 2017, utilizing 84 months of available data. The results from this study showed TEC have their lowest values during the post-midnight hours (02:00UT) and highest values during the pre-noon hours (11:00UT). We also observed that Equinoxes have high value of TEC than Solstices except during the ascending and maximum phases where seasonal/winter anomalies were recorded. From our statistical analysis, MAE was observed to give error value of ~3 TECU (TEC units) lower than the RMSE. Also from this result, we concluded that MAE is a better statistical metric than RMSE. IRI-Plas2017 outperformed IRI-2016 and NeQuick-2 models in predicting TEC values in East Africa during solar cycle 24, with a 71.4% better performance compared to other models.

Keywords: TEC. GPS. RMSE. MAE .IRI-2016 .IRI-Plas2017. NeQuick-2.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ionosphere is a region of the Earth's upper atmosphere that contains a relatively high concentration of ions and free electrons [106], [65], [90], [92], [46]. It begins at an altitude of approximately 30 miles (50 kilometers) above the Earth's surface and extend to several hundred miles (several hundred kilometers). The ionosphere plays a crucial role in various atmospheric and electromagnetic phenomena and is of significant importance for radio wave propagation, telecommunications and space weather [87]. The ionosphere has different latitudinal regions which includes the high ,mid and low/equatorial regions. The equatorial/low latitude region is a distinct and most dynamic part of the Earth's ionosphere

that spans the region around the Earth's equator [86], [30], [9], [108], [80], [39], [101], [51]. This region is characterized by unique ionospheric features and behavior due to its proximity to the equator and the interplay of various factors including solar radiation, geomagnetic effects, and atmospheric dynamics [77], [52], [59]. One of the prominent and unique features in this region is the Equatorial Ionization Anomaly (EIA). Equatorial Ionization Anomaly (E.I.A) refers to a specific pattern of electron density variations in the F2-layer of the ionosphere that is characterized by an increase in electron density during the daytime compared to the nighttime which is typically within about $\pm 20^\circ$ latitude from the equator [35], [70], [110], [7], [1], [84], [2], [69], [120], [3]. A physical mechanism known as the E X B drift is related to the mobility of charged particles (ions and electrons) in the ionosphere of the Earth as a result of the combined electric (E) and magnetic (B) fields present in that area of the atmosphere [43]. The E X B drift is an essential phenomenon to comprehending the motion and distribution of charged particles in the low latitude/equatorial region of the ionosphere, including their motion and distribution [3]. The effects of this motion on phenomena including the development of ionospheric plasma structures, the motion of plasma bubbles, and the influence on radio wave propagation and communication systems can all be considered [19]. To comprehend ionospheric dynamics and its effects on numerous technologies that depend on ionospheric conditions, researchers and scientists examine the E x B drift [39]. This unique feature and many other ionospheric dynamics leads large fluctuations in the radio wave along the satellite propagation signal paths [113], [62], [19], [6]. These fluctuations in signals will in turns lead to ionospheric delay error in signals which will invariably cause variations in ionospheric parameters such as electron or Total Electron Content (TEC). Total Electron Content (TEC) is the number of electrons present along the path between the satellite transmitter and ground base receiver [9], [13], [112], [111], [91]. This delay experienced by the signals travelling through the ionosphere along the signal path between the satellite and the receiver on the ground is proportional to TEC [114], [37], [54], [41], [18]. Therefore, the differential GPS signal delay (psedo-range) or the differential phase advance (carrier phase measurements) of the dual frequencies (1.5754 GHz and 1.2276 GHz) can be applied to derive the TEC along the signal path [4], [113], [86]. Apart from the GPS measurements of TEC, empirical models such as IRI, IRI-Plas and NeQuick models are widely used to study the variations of the ionospheric parameters (such as TEC) particularly in areas real-time measurements are not available [87], [104], [21], [48], [50], [94], [56]. There have been several ionospheric models used in predicting the true state of the ionosphere but their optimal performances are still a major setback in low/equatorial region particularly in the African region. This problem is due to the scarcity of real time input data in the models [79], [64]. Ionospheric modelling is important because it is a major tool in space weather prediction, navigations and surveillance systems [38], [28], [55], [75].

One of the most common and widely used model is the International Reference Ionosphere (IRI), meanwhile this model is updated from time to time. The International Reference Ionosphere (IRI) model is a global model developed by the International Union of Radio Science (URSI) and Committee on Space Research (COSPAR) [23], [24], [25]. The IRI model provides a reference representation of the ionosphere based on a combination of measured data and empirical formulae. It covers a wide range of ionospheric parameters such as electron density, electron temperature, and ion composition. [16], [22].

The NeQuick is an ionospheric model that is specifically designed for the predictions of electron density in the ionosphere. It was developed by the European Space Agency (ESA) and the European Telecommunication Standard Institutes (ETSI) for radio wave propagation and communication system design purposes [100], [117], [82].

[32] established that both IRI and NeQuick-2 models has same level of performance in the oceania region. They also compared their results with experimental results from Jason2/3 ionospheric data between 2002 to 2018. They concluded that IRI and NeQuick-2 models underestimate TEC but reflect long-term average condition of the ionosphere. [116] reported in their work that IRI-2016 is a good climate model that can provide accurate estimates of ionospheric delays of radio signal propagated over Pakistan in the Asian sector during the descending phase of solar cycle 24 (2015-2017). They also affirmed in their study that IRI-2016 model shows a better agreement with measured TEC around 06:00UT- 12:00UT. [105] also carried out a research at Pakistan and they came to conclusion that IRI-2016 model performed better IRI-2007 and IRI-2012 models in monthly values of TEC during the descending phase of solar cycle 24 (2019-2020). [16] reported that IRI-2016 and IRI-Plas2017 models are not superior to each other in comparison with experimental TEC (Ionolab) when the plasmapheric effect are neglected and their predictive power depends on availability of data. Meanwhile, [16] still further stated that IRI-2001 topside option of the IRI-2016 model is better in predicting TEC than the IRI01-Corr and NeQuick topside option at Istanbul (Turkey). [45] also reported in their work that IRI-Plas2017 performs better than NeQuick-2

model for low latitude stations during June solstice while the reverse was observed for high latitude station, meanwhile during September equinox their performance does not follow a definite pattern as observed in other seasons. In the work of Bolaji et al. (2017), they concluded that the NeQuick-2 model does not have the capability to predict the EIA crest pattern in northern or southern hemisphere in the African region. [87] uses GNSS/GPS data to assess the performance of IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models in six different longitudinal sectors covering 36 GNSS receiver stations for a period of 2006 to 2017 (4497 months of available data) and they concluded from their results that NeQuick-2 model performed better in 83% of the months while IRI-Plas2017 had 17% performance. [86] adopted the comparative analysis of IRI-2016 and IRI-Plas2017 models with GPS-TEC in the Europe, Africa and Asia longitude and they concluded that IRI-2016 performs better than IRI-Plas2017 in all the longitudinal sectors. [85] in their own research reported that Observed-TEC (OBS-TEC) and IRI-2016 model VTEC rise from a minimum value in the early hours to broad day time maximum before falling steeply to another minimum after sunset in African (Nigeria). They attributed this phenomenon to photoionization increase produced by solar Extreme Ultraviolet (EUV) radiation. They also concluded that IRI-2016 model cannot be used as a proxy for TEC measurements for most hours of the day in Birni Kebbi (Nigeria).

Many other researchers like [20], [5], [4], [11], [14], [16], [8], [31], [83], [115], [12], [113], [76], [71], [86], [107], [53], [78], [95], [119] have studied the variations of TEC with comparison with IRI and NeQuick models in different longitudinal sectors. In recent time, only few researches have been presented in the low/equatorial latitude east African region due to its dynamic, complex nature and unavailability of measurement data hence, the need for more investigations. This paper will study the variations of TEC in a low latitude east African GPS station by comparing experimental values of TEC (GPS-TEC) with predicted TEC from IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models during three different phases (ascending, maximum, and descending) of solar cycle 24 using two different standard metric of measurement (RMSE and MAE). The results from this research will reveal the predictive level of IRI and NeQuick models and suggest their possible upgrade and update which will make the study of ionospheric activities easier even in areas where GPS stations are not present in the African sector.

2. DATA AND METHOD OF ANALYSIS

In this research work, the two types of ionospheric data used were the observed data, which is the GPS-TEC, and the predicted ionospheric data from an East Africa GPS station, Addis Ababa (ADIS) between 2011 to 2017, with coordinates of geographic longitude and latitude of 38.77°E, 9.04°N, and geomagnetic longitude and latitude of 110.83°E, 31.75°N, respectively. The observed data is the GPS data, which is obtained from the University NAVSTAR Consortium (UNAVCO) website at <http://www.unavco.org>, while the predicted data used in this research work are the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and the NeQuick-2 models. The NeQuick-2 model is an improved and updated version of the NeQuick model [82], [99], [96]. The hourly TEC values of IRI-2016 were obtained from the Community Coordinating Modeling Center (CCMC) website (https://ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov/modelweb/models/iri2016_vitmo.php) using IRI-2001 topside option. The IRI-Plas 2017 computes TEC data up to a height of 20,200km. Also, hourly TEC values for the IRI-Plas 2017 model were obtained using the windows executable program from the website of the IZMIRAN Institute (<http://ftp.izmiran.ru/pub/izmiran/SPIM/>) [16]. While, hourly TEC values of NeQuick-2 were obtained using the windows executable program created from the FORTRAN source code, which was obtained from the Ionosphere Radio Propagation Unit of the T/ICT4D Laboratory ([https://t-ict4d.ictp.it/nequick2/source code](https://t-ict4d.ictp.it/nequick2/source%20code)). GPS-TEC were downloaded in Receiver Independent Exchange (RINEX) format and were processed using GPS-TEC analysis software (GPS_Gopi_v3.03), designed and developed by Gopi Seemala of the Indian Institute of Geomagnetism and accessible from his webpage (<https://seemala.blogspot.com>). The summary of the GPS-TEC application software is to read raw data from the RINEX file, process cycle slips, multipath, and scintillations, and then produce output TEC values [87], [85]. According to [86] and [101], an elevation cut-off angles greater than 50° is required for an ionospheric shell height of about 350km for the low/equatorial-latitude region of the ionosphere. GPS-TEC obtained from the GPS-TEC analysis software are in per minute sequence, which were averaged to hourly TEC values using equation 1. Also, equation 1 was used to convert hourly TEC values of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas 2017 and NeQuick-2 models to monthly TEC values.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (TEC_i) \quad (1)$$

The hourly values of GPS-TEC, IRI-2016, IRI-Plas 2017 and NeQuick-2 were used to study the diurnal variations in TEC. Furthermore, the hourly TEC values were averaged to daily values and further averaged to monthly values. The monthly

TEC values were further grouped into the four seasons namely: March equinox (February, March, and April), June solstice (May, June, and July), September equinox (August, September, and October) and December solstice (November, December, and January) as shown in Table 1, in order to analyze the seasonal variations in TEC.

Table 1: The four Seasons of the year with their corresponding months.

S/N	Seasons	Months
1	March Equinox	February, March, April
2	June Solstice	May, June, July
3	September Equinox	August, September, October
4	December Solstice	November, December, January

To investigate the performances of the ionospheric models, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) were used.

RMSE is calculated using equation 2.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\sum_i^N \frac{(TEC_{model_i} - TEC_{gps_i})^2}{N}} \quad (2)$$

Where TEC_{model_i} is the TEC data from IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models while TEC_{gps_i} is the TEC data from GPS and N is the number of hours per day.

The MAE was calculated using equation 3.

$$MAE = [n^{-1} \sum_i^n (y_i - x_i)] \quad (3)$$

where y_i is the prediction, x_i true value and n is the total number of data points.

The Percentage Deviation is the degree of how the models deviated from the GPS-TEC value given by equation 4

$$percentage\ Deviation = \left(\frac{GPS - Model}{GPS} \right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

TEC Deviation is also employ to investigate the difference in the TEC value between the GPS and modelled TEC and given by equation 5

$$TEC\ Deviation = GPS_{observed} - Model_{predicted} \quad (5)$$

Table 2: The years, Solar Cycle Phase and Sunspot number.

S/N	Years	Solar Cycle Phase	Sunspot Number(R_z)
1	2011	Ascending	55.6
2	2012	Ascending	57.6
3	2013	Ascending	64.7
4	2014	Maximum	79.6
5	2015	Maximum	69.9
6	2016	Descending	39.9
7	2017	Descending	21.8

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Diurnal and Seasonal Variations in TEC

Fig. 1 Diurnal and Seasonal Variations in TEC at ADIS in 2011

Fig. 2 Diurnal and Seasonal Variations in TEC at ADIS in 2012

Fig. 3 Diurnal and Seasonal Variations in TEC at ADIS in 2013

Fig. 4 Diurnal and Seasonal Variations in TEC at ADIS in 2014

Fig. 5 Diurnal and Seasonal Variations in TEC at ADIS in 2015

Fig. 6 Diurnal and Seasonal Variations in TEC at ADIS in 2016

Fig. 7 Diurnal and Seasonal Variations in TEC at ADIS in 2017

Fig. 1-7 shows the diurnal and seasonal variations in TEC between 2011 to 2017. The years 2011 to 2013 is the ascending solar activity phase. In this solar cycle phase, GPS-TEC experiences equinoctial asymmetry, except in 2012 where it was pronounced during the March equinox for GPS-TEC values. Equinoctial asymmetry is a phenomenon whereby the two equinoxes (March and September Equinox) records different range values of TEC [40], [44], [102], [27], [72]. This is as a result of the differences in the meridional winds which in turn leads to changes in the neutral gas composition during equinoxes [85], [73]. Equinoctial asymmetry can also be attributed to the fact that the height of F layer is higher during vernal equinox as compared to autumn equinoxes [109], [43]. The IRI-2016 and IRI-Plas2017 models mostly overestimate GPS-TEC during the morning hours (02:00UT-06:00UT) and night period (15:00UT-23:00UT) of the day. The NeQuick-2 had a good agreement with GPS-TEC during the early morning hours of the day (01:00UT-06:00UT). The IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models mostly underestimates GPS-TEC around the noon period (12:00UT). The highest overestimations of GPS-TEC recorded during this solar cycle phase was also around the noon period particularly during the June solstice. The IRI-Plas2017 model slightly overestimates GPS-TEC around the noon period during the equinox months except during the September equinox month in 2013 where it recorded ~5 TECU higher than the GPS-TEC. The years 2014 and 2015 recorded the highest average annual sunspot number which makes the values of TEC to be higher than other solar cycle phases. The highest peak value of GPS-TEC was recorded during the March equinox season of both years as ~85 TECU while the highest values of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models were recorded as ~60 TECU, ~61 TECU

and 41 TECU respectively. Semi Annual variation anomaly was recorded during this maximum phase (2014 and 2015) due to the slightly lower values of TEC recorded during the September equinox when compared to the equinox seasons. This phenomenon is attributed to the fact the solar zenith angle of sun is lower during the equinox season and higher during the solstice seasons [60], [98]. The descending phase of the solar cycle (2016 and 2017) experiences a fall in the value of TEC which was as a result of drop in the sunspot number [49], [89], [15], [93], [66], [97]. The highest peak value of TEC recorded in this phase was ~67 TECU during the September equinox around the noon period (12:00UT) from the GPS-TEC while the lowest value of TEC recorded was observed from the NeQuick-2 model around the post-midnight period (02:00UT). This lowest value was recorded as ~3 TECU around the same time frame for all seasons and in all the solar cycle phases from the NeQuick-2 model in this research. Generally, winter anomaly was observed in all the phases of the solar cycle except during the descending phase. Winter anomaly is a phenomenon where the December solstice TEC value is greater than the June solstice [57], [42], [90], [67]. This is as a result of the variations in the neutral composition (O/N_2 ratio) at thermospheric height [85],[36], [88], [118]. Night time enhancement was also observed in all the phases of the solar cycle which is as a result of irregularities in the electron distributions in the F-region of the ionosphere during the night period [74], [17], [68], [33]. This physical phenomenon is more pronounced and stronger during the ascending phase and weakest during the descending phase. Equatorial noon bite-out is another prominent phenomenon observed mostly during the June and December solstice during the ascending and maximum/descending phases of the solar cycle. It is a physical mechanism that is most observed in the equatorial low latitude region in the ionosphere, which is as a result of EXB drift leading to fountain effect in the F-region [61], [34], [58], [81]. Generally, the IRI and NeQuick models manifested a daytime underestimations and nighttime overestimations of TEC, which is similar to the results reported by [103] and [114].

3.2 Percentage Deviations of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models from GPS-TEC

Fig. 8 Monthly Percentage Deviations of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick-2 models from GPS-TEC during the ascending phase

Fig. 9 Monthly Percentage Deviations of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick models from GPS-TEC during the maximum phase

Fig. 10 Monthly Percentage Deviations of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick models from GPS-TEC during the descending phase

Fig. 8-10 indicates the monthly percentage deviations of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models from GPS-TEC during ascending, maximum and descending phases. On the figure legend, iri2016dev, iriplas2017dev and Nequickdev denotes the deviations of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models from GPS values. During the ascending phase, the IRI-2016 and IRI-Plas2017 models predictions were good during the daytime between 06:00UT to 15:00UT hours of the day but their predictions were generally poor for all the months and they recorded overestimations of GPS-TEC during the early morning hours between (01:00T -05:00UT) and during the night hours between 16:00UT -24:00UT except the month of November where the IRI-Plas2017 model had the best performance. The NeQuick-2 model had the best performance between 15:00UT- 17:00UT hours of the day all throughout the months of the year except for the month of November where it had a worst performance and recorded underestimations of GPS-TEC during the day between 03:00UT-16:00UT and overestimations during the early morning hours (01:00UT-02:00UT) and night hours between (17:00UT-24:00UT). A very high deviations were observed during the months of August and October from the IRI-2016 model where its overestimations increases by 756% and 656% during the early morning hours of the day respectively. This is attributed to the absence of plasmapheric content input parameter in the models for these months [10], [63], [47]. Almost similar deviations were observed during the maximum and descending phases but with slight variations as were recorded during the ascending phase. Generally, the performances of models were good during the day time and poor during the early morning and night time hours.

3.3 Annual Deviations of the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick-2 from GPS-TEC

Fig. 11 Annual Deviations of the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick-2 from GPS-TEC at ADIS for the year 2011

Fig. 12 Annual Deviations of the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick from GPS-TEC at ADIS for the year 2012

Fig. 13 Annual Deviations of the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick from GPS-TEC at ADIS for the year 2013

Fig. 14 Annual Deviations of the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick from GPS-TEC at ADIS for the year 2014

Fig. 15 Anual Deviations of the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick from GPS-TEC at ADIS for the year 2015

Fig. 16 Anual Deviations of the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick from GPS-TEC at ADIS for the year 2016

Fig. 17 Annual Deviations of the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick from GPS-TEC at ADIS for the year 2017

Fig. 11-17 illustrates the annual deviation of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models from GPS-TEC at ADIS from 2011 to 2017. From Fig. 15- 21, brownish red color indicates slight overestimations of GPS-TEC by IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models which invariably indicates a fair performance of the model, while the brown color indicates very high overestimations of GPS-TEC data thus, a worst performance of the model. The yellow color denotes no deviation of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models from GPS-TEC hence, best performance. The light blue color indicates a slight underestimation (fair performance of the model), while dark blue color shows a highest underestimations (poor performance of the model). The white patches from the mass plots indicates that no data were recorded during that time of the day. The highest during of missing data recorded was during 2015 from 24:00UT to 13:00UT in the month of August. In 2011, data were not recorded for 7hours (16:00UT-23:00T) in November. The same during of missing data were recorded in 2012 and 2014 between 02:00UT and 07:00UT in July and January respectively. The year 2013 recorded missing data in two different consecutive months (August and September) from 20:00UT to 23:00UT and 02:00UT to 12:00UT respectively. The year 2017 recorded the highest availability of data. From this analysis, we confirm that the IRI-Plas2017 model had the best performance from 2011 to 2017 except for year 2015 where the IRI-2016 and IRI-Plas2017 models had exactly the same level of performance as reported in the work of [87].

3.4 Annual Root Mean Square Error for IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models

Fig. 18 Annual Root Mean Square Error for IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick models at ADIS from 2011-2017

Fig. 18 shows the annual Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models at ADIS from 2011 to 2017. In the year 2011, the IRI-Plas2017 model had the lowest RMSE value throughout the months of the year except in the month of June, July and August where the NeQuick-2 model recorded the lowest RMSE values. In the month of November, the performance of the IRI-Plas2017 model was worst with a value recorded as ~21 TECU which was the highest value recorded from any model all through out the year. Almost similar features were recorded from 2012 to 2014 except in 2013 where the highest RMSE value shifted to the month of December from the NeQuick-2 model. In the year 2015, the highest value from the RMSE analysis was still recorded from the NeQuick-2 model in the month of May with a value of ~37 TECU but in 2016, the highest RMSE from the NeQuick-2 model shifted again to the month of October. Lastly, the year 2017 had a change in the highest value of RMSE recorded. This year, the highest RMSE recorded ~17 TECU from the IRI-2016 model while the least RMSE was recorded during the month of June with ~3 TECU as its value.

3.5 Annual Root Mean Square Error for IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models

Fig. 19 Annual Mean Absolute Error for IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick models at ADIS from 2011-2017

Fig. 19 depicts the annual Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models at ADIS from 2011 to 2017. The MAE is employed to further investigate the degree of deviations of the IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017 and NeQuick-2 models from GPS-TEC and in the same vain to show the level of their performance. From our results, we concluded that MAE values were ~3 TECU lower than the RMSE in all the solar cycle phases. Also, from the results presented here, we affirm that MAE can better assess the performance of a model than RMSE. Our affirmation was in agreement with the work of [29].

Table 3: The Annual performance of IRI-Plas2017, IRI-2016, and NeQuick at ADIS

S/N	YEAR	IRI-Plas2017	IRI-2016	NeQUICK
1	2011	62.7%	4.2%	33.1%
2	2012	75%	5%	20%
3	2013	66.7%	16.7%	16.6%
4	2014	81.3%	16.2%	2.5%
5	2015	48%	48%	4%
6	2016	81.3%	16.2%	2.5%
7	2017	72%	5%	23%

The percentage performance of IRI-Plas2017, IRI-2016 and NeQuick-2 models in all the months for 7 years at ADIS in the east African region is shown in table 3. The table clearly indicates that IRI-Plas2017 model had the best performances in all the months from 2011 to 2017 over the IRI-2016 and NeQuick-2 models. It also clearly depicts that the IRI-Plas2017 model had its best performance of 81.3% in 2016 while the NeQuick-2 had the worst performance of 2.5% in the same year.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this present study, we have analyzed the performance of IRI-2016, IRI-Plas2017, and NeQuick-2 models using GPS-TEC data in the East African low latitude region (Addis Ababa) during solar cycle 24 (2011-2017). We affirmed that the lowest TEC values (as low as ~2 TECU from the NeQuick-2 model) were recorded around the post-midnight period (02:00UT) while the highest values (as high as ~85 TECU from GPS-TEC) of TEC were recorded around the pre-noon period (11:00UT). Seasonally, we infer that equinoxes recorded higher values of TEC than solstice seasons but seasonal/winter anomaly were encountered by the TEC values in all the phases of the solar cycle except during the descending phase. Nighttime enhancement is more pronounced and stronger during the ascending phase and weakest during the descending phase. Also from our results, MAE gives values ~3 TECU lower than those of the RMSE. From the results of our statistically analysis, we deduced that the IRI-Plas2017 model had the best performance of 71.4% of the months while the IRI-2016 and NeQuick-2 model had same performance of 14.3% each of the months under consideration. Conclusively, IRI-Plas2017 model predicts TEC better than the IRI-2016 and NeQuick-2 models in the East African region. The poor performance of IRI-2016 model from this research work has proven that NeQuick topside option of the model (IRI-2016) is accurate and better in predicting TEC in the East African region than the IRI-2001 topside option as reported by [10]. Also, the low predictive power of the NeQuick-2 model is as a result of low data input into the model during its validation process.

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Authors Contributions

Y.O.K, E.O, and O.O analyzed data, plotted the figures and wrote the initial manuscript. S.A.O and A.S.A wrote part of the methodology while R.B.A and R.A.A proof read and corrected the entire grammatical arrangements of the manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest

The Authors declare no conflict or competing interest

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